

SOCIAL SCIENCES

A STUDY ON THE OPERATIONAL CHARACTERISTICS OF WECHAT "CONFESSION WALLS" IN UNIVERSITIES AND THEIR GOVERNANCE IN ONLINE EDUCATION—TAKING HETAO COLLEGE AS AN EXAMPLE

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Abstract

With the popularization of social media, WeChat "confession walls" for college students, as a representative virtual social platform on campus, have rapidly developed and spread widely within universities. While meeting the needs of college students for emotional expression, information exchange, and resource sharing, the platform's openness and anonymity also bring new challenges to university network governance and public opinion management. This paper takes Hetao University as a case study, selects three representative WeChat "confession wall" platforms on campus, conducts text and word frequency analysis of their content published in 2023, systematically sorts out the main functional types of university WeChat "confession walls," deeply analyzes the problems existing in their operation, and proposes corresponding governance strategies from three levels: university management, student subjects, and platform technical support. The research aims to provide practical reference for universities to standardize the management of campus social media platforms and optimize the online educational environment.

Keywords: University WeChat "confession wall"; virtual community; social media governance; anonymity;

1. Research Background and Problem Statement

With the rapid development of the internet and information technology online virtual communities such as forums, online communities, QQ, and WeChat have emerged, profoundly changing people's social interaction methods and gradually becoming important spaces for individuals to express their demands, exchange opinions, and build social relationships. According to the 56th Statistical Report on Internet Development in China released by the China Internet Network Information Center (CNNIC), as of June 2025, the number of internet users in China reached 1.123 billion, with an internet penetration rate of 79.7%, of which 99.4% accessed the internet via mobile phones. In terms of age structure, internet users aged 20-29 accounted for 13.7%¹, and university students constitute a significant young group of internet users. Against this backdrop, WeChat has gradually become one of the most frequently used social platforms among university students. Among the various virtual campus communities derived from WeChat, platforms centered on "expression of thoughts," such as "confession walls," "all-purpose walls," and "information sharing walls," stand out. These platforms are typically operated spontaneously by students or on-campus businesses, existing in the form of WeChat official accounts or mini-programs, targeting specific university student groups and providing services such as emotional expression, information dissemination, and resource sharing. Due to their close connection to students' daily lives, low barriers to interaction, and high dissemination efficiency, they have

gradually become unofficial online spaces with significant influence within universities. Taking Hetao College as an example, the "confession wall" platforms on campus have maintained high activity levels for a long time, but their content publishing and operational management have not yet been incorporated into the school's formal governance system, and related risks are gradually emerging. Against this backdrop, this paper selects three representative thought expression platforms of Hetao College—"Hetao College Confession Wall," "Hetao College All-Purpose Platform," and "Hetao College Confession Wall 2"—as research objects, conducts word frequency analysis of their published content in 2023, systematically reviews the main functional forms of university WeChat "thought expression platforms," and conducts an in-depth analysis of the potential risks in their operation.

2. Main Functions of University WeChat "Confession Wall"

2.1 Information Dissemination and Resource Sharing Functions

The most basic and common function of university WeChat "confession walls" lies in information reception and dissemination. Platform operators centrally collect and publish student submissions, enabling information that was previously scattered among individuals to circulate rapidly within the campus, forming a high-frequency, real-time campus information dissemination network. Related content mainly covers lost and found, carpooling, job and part-time job postings, sharing of learning materials, course Q&A, and activity team formation, basically covering the high-frequency needs of university students in their daily studies and lives.

¹ 56th Statistical Report on Internet Development in China. <https://www.cnnic.net.cn/n4/2025/0721/c88-11328.html>

From a dissemination perspective, WeChat "confession walls" operate on a familiar social platform, with a relatively stable and targeted audience. Information dissemination is highly targeted and has a fast response time, enabling effective information delivery in a short period. This "one-to-many" dissemination method, to some extent, overcomes the limitations of official university information release channels in terms of timeliness and flexibility, making up for the "micro-needs" and "temporary needs" that formal notification systems cannot cover.

From a functional value perspective, the information dissemination and resource sharing functions not only improve the efficiency of resource allocation within the campus but also, to some extent, enhance students' awareness of mutual assistance and group identity. Through information sharing and mutual assistance facilitated by the platform, university WeChat "confession walls" have gradually evolved into comprehensive virtual campus communities that integrate information services, life assistance, and emotional connections, playing an irreplaceable supplementary role in students' daily lives.

2.2 Emotional Expression and Social Interaction Functions

The functions of emotional expression and social interaction are among the core features that distinguish the WeChat "Confession Wall" in universities from general information platforms. In the relatively closed but highly familiar campus network environment, the WeChat "Confession Wall" provides university students with a low-threshold, weakly constrained space for emotional expression, allowing them to openly or semi-openly express their feelings about friendship, love, interpersonal relationships, and personal emotional states. Related content mainly includes confessions of love, friendly interactions, emotional outpourings, finding specific partners, and emotional expressions about campus life.

From the perspective of the interaction mechanism, the WeChat "Confession Wall" usually supports anonymous or semi-anonymous submissions, which to some extent reduces the psychological pressure on students when expressing their emotions, especially helping them express emotions and demands that are difficult to express directly in real life. The anonymity mechanism not only provides privacy protection for students but also enhances the participation and topicality of the platform's content, maintaining a high level of activity in emotional interaction.

From the perspective of social interaction functions, the "Confession Wall" not only carries the expression of romantic feelings but also becomes an important medium for students to expand their social relationships and build campus social networks. Through continuous interaction, the platform subtly strengthens emotional connections and group identity among students, enabling individuals to receive emotional responses and social support in the virtual space. However, while this function brings positive impacts, it also poses potential risks such as amplified emotions, biased public opinion, and even online conflicts, which require attention from university management.

2.3 Indirect Commodity Exchange and Service Information Functions

Beyond information dissemination and emotional interaction, the university WeChat "Confession Wall" has gradually evolved into a function for indirect commodity exchange and service information dissemination, primarily within the campus. From the platform's content structure, keywords related to "for sale," "want to buy," "transfer," "second-hand," "carpooling," and "delivery pickup" appear frequently, reflecting students' real needs for goods circulation and mutual service assistance on the platform.

In practice, students use the "Confession Wall" to post information about the sale of second-hand items such as textbooks, study materials, and daily necessities, effectively promoting the reuse of idle resources and reducing students' living costs. Simultaneously, the dissemination of service-oriented information such as delivery pickup, carpooling, and temporary assistance also alleviates the problems of students' time constraints and fragmented tasks to some extent, demonstrating the platform's strong life service attributes.

From the perspective of functional evolution, the indirect commodity exchange and service information functions have transformed the university WeChat "Confession Wall" from a simple platform for emotional expression into a comprehensive campus virtual community with both information services and life support functions. However, due to the lack of formal regulatory mechanisms for related transactions and services, the platform also faces problems such as transaction disputes and insufficient information authenticity in actual operation, which poses new requirements for the governance of cyberspace in universities.

Figure 1: Frequency analysis of words on the "Confession Wall" WeChat account of Hetao College

Figure 2: Frequency analysis of the "All-Purpose Wall" on the Hetao College WeChat account

Figure 3: Frequency analysis of the WeChat account "All-Purpose Wall 2" of Hetao College

3.Problems and Countermeasures of WeChat "Confession Walls" in Universities

While university WeChat "confession walls" have played a positive role in meeting the diverse needs of

university students for information exchange, emotional expression, and resource sharing, their operation has also exposed a series of problems due to the platform's unique characteristics. Specifically, WeChat "confession walls" mostly rely on unofficial accounts,

exhibiting significant virtual, anonymous, and decentralized features. The low barrier to entry for content posting and relatively weak review mechanisms make them prone to risks such as the spread of false information, online verbal abuse, infringement of personal privacy, and disordered public opinion. These problems not only affect the healthy operation of the platform itself but also pose new challenges to the governance of university cyberspace and the construction of a conducive educational environment. Therefore, it is necessary to construct a multi-stakeholder collaborative governance mechanism, involving university management departments, students, and platform technical support, to promote the standardized development of university WeChat "confession walls."

3.1 University Level: Strengthening Guidance and Institutional Development

In the current operation of university WeChat "confession walls," these platforms are mostly operated spontaneously by individual students or on-campus businesses, lacking clear management boundaries and responsible parties. This leads to the easy occurrence of false information, infringing statements, and negative value orientations during content posting. Therefore, universities should explore establishing a relatively flexible management and guidance mechanism while fully respecting students' right to reasonable expression.

On the one hand, universities can use methods such as registration and communication to gain a basic understanding of active "confession wall" platforms on campus, clarifying the platform's operating entity and basic norms, laying the foundation for subsequent governance. On the other hand, universities should strengthen education on cybersecurity, laws and regulations, and media literacy. Through special lectures, course integration, and themed activities, universities can improve students' awareness of the boundaries of online speech and legal risks. Simultaneously, universities can utilize psychological counseling and ideological and political education resources to guide students to express emotions rationally and participate in interactions civilly, avoiding the excessive amplification of negative emotions in cyberspace. In addition, universities can provide positive incentives to platforms and individuals that consistently spread positive energy and serve the needs of students through publicity and recommendations, thereby creating a positive demonstration effect in the campus cyberspace.

3.2 Student Level: Enhancing Self-Discipline and Rational Participation Ability

Students are not only the primary users of the university's WeChat "Confession Wall" but also important producers of platform content. Their behavior largely determines the overall character of the platform. Therefore, enhancing students' self-discipline and rational participation is crucial for the platform's healthy development.

In practice, students should consciously abide by basic online ethics and legal norms, avoiding the publication of false information, offensive statements, or content that infringes on others' privacy. They should

maintain rational restraint and mutual respect in expressing emotions and stating opinions. Simultaneously, students should actively participate in platform governance, providing feedback on inappropriate information through reporting and reminders, working with universities and the platform to maintain a healthy online environment. By improving individual media literacy and public awareness, and promoting the transformation of students from mere "content publishers" to "responsible participants," we can help build a healthier and more orderly campus online community.

3.3 Platform Level: Providing Technical Support and Rule Guarantees

As the technical foundation for the operation of university WeChat "confession walls," the WeChat platform also plays a crucial role in content governance and risk control. On the one hand, the platform can leverage algorithms, keyword filtering, and other technologies to enhance the automatic identification and risk warning of inappropriate information, improving the timeliness and effectiveness of content review. On the other hand, it should continuously improve platform usage guidelines, clearly defining prohibited information types and behavioral boundaries, and enhancing users' awareness of rules through prominent prompts.

Furthermore, the WeChat platform can explore establishing cooperation mechanisms with universities to provide more refined management tools and data support for campus accounts, such as content review assistance functions and risk warning mechanisms, helping universities better understand the platform's operation. By combining technical governance with rule guidance, the university WeChat "confession walls" can achieve standardized operation and controllable risks while ensuring freedom of expression.

University WeChat "confession walls" are a new phenomenon on campus networks that has emerged alongside the development of social media. Research has found that this platform is not only an important carrier for university students' emotional expression and social interaction but also a window into the campus cultural ecology and students' psychological state. Its content structure exhibits characteristics of information exchange, emotional interaction, and resource sharing, but it also faces the problem of insufficient governance norms. Multi-stakeholder collaborative governance can help protect students' right to expression while promoting the orderly operation and value guidance of university cyberspace. This research provides a practical reference for university social media governance and online education practices.

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